

QED origin of gravitational field and exotic consequences

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Abstract

We search, in elementary charged particles, a derivation of gravity from QED, starting with classical electrostatic force at a classic electromagnetic radius distance, with a Planck length uncertainty. Noting a possibility for a second order QED term, multiplying the term for the fine structure constant, we obtain self gravitational force, then gravitational field. It follows that massive not-charged elementary particles, such as neutrino, don't have a gravitational field.

1 Introduction

Quantum gravity and unification between electromagnetic and gravitational field are goals pursued for a long time. Changing point of view, we have searched a derivation of gravitational from electromagnetic field, rather than a high temperature, gauge or multi-dimensional unification. Some phenomena connected with equivalence principle seem to support this.

Starting with electrostatic force at r_0 (classical radius) distance, between two charged particles, and with an uncertainty l (the smallest length in nature), quantitatively l_P , we obtain a medium F containing a gravitational term multiplied by $\frac{1}{\alpha}$. We better interpret this result, multiplying for α , as a self electromagnetic and gravitational interaction in QED context. A second order virtual electromagnetic self interaction implies virtual mediators with a total spin = 2. To obtain coherent results we have to consider complex numbers into equations.

A strange consequence of this derivation from QED, in elementary particles, is the absence of gravitational field for not-charged massive elementary particles, such as neutrino. Relativity principle and energy conservation principle is also questioned.

2 Correlation between electromagnetic and gravitational field

There are some aspects contributing to think of a correlation between electromagnetic and gravitational field.

- Newton and Coulomb laws have the same form.
- Electromagnetic inertial mass and corresponding quantum self-energy for charged particles has to be connected to the gravitational mass, in agreement with equivalence principle.
- A Photon acquiring energy in a gravitational field is indistinguishable from a photon with the same energy locally emitted by a system of charges.
- A system accelerated by a force, for example electromagnetic, produce, in agreement with general relativity principle for a system-bound observer, a gravitational field. Furthermore, a mass accelerating in this field, then attracted by the gravitational force, for the 3rd Newton principle (action and reaction), does also have a gravitational field. So we could think it is produced, ultimately, by an electromagnetic force field.

3 Electrostatic force at $r_0 \pm l_P$ distance

We assume the existence of a length, a fundamental space uncertainty, that is the smallest of all lengths, but finite (not infinitesimal). Then $\Delta x = l > 0$, $l \in \mathbb{R}$. This can be justified by usual concreteness, for which an infinitesimal (or infinite) value doesn't exist (but see also [2] for a dynamical rational explanation and [1]). This causes problems about determining the central value in Coulomb Law measure. In fact considering the spatial position r_0 that represents the best value (referring to the theory of errors) inside the interval $r_0 - l, r_0 + l$, the corresponding $F_{r_0} (= \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2})$ is not the F best value

in the same interval, but it is:

$$\bar{F} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0(r_0-l+\frac{n2l}{N})^2}}{N} = -\frac{1}{2l} \int_{r_0-l}^{r_0+l} \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} dr = \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0(r_0^2 - l^2)} \quad (1)$$

(With $N \rightarrow \infty$). That is the average of all F values in the interval r_0-l, r_0+l .

We have considered $N = \frac{2l}{dr}$. \bar{F} is the best force value for the distance r_0 in the interval $2l$ and $\bar{F} \neq F_{r_0}$. Each value into the interval $2l$ has to have the same observability frequency, otherwise the uncertainty l could be further reduced in principle.

$\frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0(r_0^2 - l^2)} \simeq \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2} + \frac{l^2 q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^4}$, in second approximation. Now, multiplying for α ($= \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar c}$), taking $|q_1| = |q_2| = q$, $m_0 c^2 = \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0}$ and $l = l_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}$ (Planck length), we get:

$$\alpha \cdot \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0(r_0^2 - l^2)} \simeq \frac{\alpha \cdot q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2} + G \frac{m_{01} m_{02}}{r_0^2} \quad (2)$$

being $\frac{\alpha(l_P)^2 q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^4} = \frac{\alpha(l_P)^2 q_1^2 q_2^2}{(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_0^4} \cdot \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0}{q_1 q_2} = \frac{\alpha 4\pi\epsilon_0 (l_P)^2 c^4}{q^2} \cdot \frac{m_{01} m_{02}}{r_0^2} = G \frac{m_{01} m_{02}}{r_0^2}$ ($m_{01} = m_{02}$).

4 Result interpretation: gravitational field

$\frac{\alpha \cdot q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$ in equation (2) could be interpreted as a second approximation term considering perturbation theory in QED, being $\frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$ the first order interaction between two charges. Then we are describing a virtual process, involving virtual photons (Fig.1).

Also the length $l = l_P$ (Planck length) would have a virtual character if we were considering not too great energy uncertainties. So, to formally distinguish an observable process (with real values) from a virtual, not directly observable one, we use a formalism with complex numbers.

To denote a physical quantity as virtual we multiply it for \sqrt{i} . We define \sqrt{i} the "virtual unity". An intuitive reason for this definition is that $\sqrt{i} \cdot (\sqrt{i})^* = 1$, the real unity ($(\sqrt{i})^*$ is the complex conjugate of \sqrt{i}), in analogy with the wave function ψ , without a physical interpretation, and $\psi\psi^*$. To denote a not observable quantity we multiply it for i . In practice we consider three levels: imaginary (not observable), complex (not directly or semi-observable, virtual), real (observable).

The classical self-interaction force term, at distance r_0 is $\frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$. The analogue QED Feynman diagram is the lowest order electron self-energy diagram (see [11] for correspondence principle), Fig 1. We can consider this self-interaction real; it is not observable only because the average contribution for all directions is null. So we admit that the second order approximation of self-interaction is $\frac{\alpha \cdot q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$, Fig. 2. But this is purely imaginary, being an approximation of a not observable process (in [11] upper orders shouldn't be involved for getting correspondence principle); in spite of the result is a real self force (with a null average contribution), the self energy process that yields exact real observable values, i.e. $m_0^{bare} \rightarrow m_0$ [8], is not observable (this is different, for example, from an observable process involving a momentum changing: $p_1 \rightarrow p_2$).

Then, modifying equation (1), we have:

$$i\alpha\bar{F}_{self} = \frac{i\alpha}{2l} \int_{r_0-\sqrt{il}}^{r_0+\sqrt{il}} \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} dr = \frac{i\alpha q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0(r_0^2 - il^2)} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{i\alpha q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0(r_0^2 - il_P^2)} \simeq \frac{i\alpha q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2} - G \frac{m_0^2}{r_0^2} \quad (4)$$

So, second order self electromagnetic force, Fig. 2, is imaginary and then not observable, but self gravitational force is real and observable.

Without using imaginary and complex numbers, we would get nonsense real, then observable terms, such as $\frac{\alpha \cdot q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$, or terms obtained with charge-charge real interactions in the presence of l_P . The real first order term, \bar{F}_{self} ($i\alpha\bar{F}_{self}$ in (3) without $i\alpha$), implies in addition to $\frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$ an imaginary not observable term.

We could interpret this "self gravitational force", in (4), $G \frac{m_0^2}{r_0^2}$, in a different manner in comparison with self electromagnetic force at the first order $\frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_0^2}$ (with a null average contribution). It is the force, acting to the charged particle m_0 with an acceleration $G \frac{m_0}{r_0^2}$, seen by an observer free falling in a free-force contour at distance r_0 from m_0 ; so as prescribed by equivalence principle and general relativity principle. Then we expect that virtual photons, fig. 2, together the presence of the smallest uncertainty l_P , influence time-space.

It is important to mark that second approximation self interaction process involves two virtual photons or a virtual photon with an e^+e^- loop, then a

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

total spin = 2, fig. 2. So graviton would be a quasi-particle. In this way time-space and its deformation seem to appear more concrete.

At distance r , greater than r_0 , interaction probability of virtual photons (see [10] for electromagnetic force) gives the force, for an observer free falling: $G \frac{m_0^2}{r^2}$. Then reciprocally, for an observer on m_0 , an acceleration of any object at distance r : $G \frac{m_0}{r^2}$. So virtual photons interact with the charged particle and extend their influence at an arbitrary distance r , producing a time-space deformation depending by $G \frac{m_0^2}{r_0^2} \cdot \frac{r_0^2}{r^2} = G \frac{m_0^2}{r^2}$. An alternative, to space propagation by virtual photons of local time-space deformation at distance r_0 , could be a local production at r_0 of virtual gravitons but without further explanations in this context.

Also gravitational field of a real photon could be due by its self interaction at second order (a virtual couple e^-e^+ together a virtual photon) considering at first a distance $\lambda \pm l_P$, but we don't treat this here.

5 Exotic consequences

We have obtained the gravitational field from charged particles self-interaction mediated by virtual photons, in the presence of the smallest uncertainty l . So a massive elementary particle if wasn't able to interact through an electro-

magnetic field, wouldn't have a gravitational field. It is the case of massive neutrino [5] [9], that interacts only by weak force (which, among other, has an exponential form, not-compatible with gravitational law). We could imagine a virtual electro-weak boson self-interacting, but long distances r , then a long range time-space deformation, cannot be considered (simply just think that two neutrinos don't interact at long distance r via weak and electromagnetic force). As already mentioned, an alternative, to space propagation by virtual photons of local time-space deformation at distance r_0 , could be a local production at r_0 of virtual gravitons but without further explanations in this context.

It could be considered that, for the absence of gravitational field, action-reaction principle is not accomplished in neutrino-matter gravitational interaction, then momentum, energy conservation principle and relativity principle are violated. For the not-conservation of energy: we could move an ordinary mass with respect to neutrino without working, however assuming a neutrino that is sensitive to gravity. At the same time a system, consisting of a neutrino and a mass in reciprocal motion, is seen acquiring (losing) kinetic energy or not changing kinetic energy, depending on the observer, in contrast with relativity principle.

Even assuming neutrino (or antineutrino) is not attracted to a gravitational field (momentum principle conservation is valid), general relativity principle is explicitly violated and also energy conservation principle can still be violated. In fact an observer, referring to a neutrino (gravitationally not interacting), could distinguish between an accelerated system and a real gravitational field. Also we can think of a neutron, falling in a gravitational field and acquiring kinetic energy, which decays in a proton, electron and an antineutrino; this last one can go back through the gravitational field without losing kinetic energy and others interactions could violate conservation energy principle.

It should be noted that massive neutrino interaction, at vary short distance and violating parity in beta decay, doesn't seem to have a classic correspondence, also regarding acceleration. We could expect a strange inertial and then gravitational behavior. For the possibility of equivalence and relativity principle violation and possible experiments see [3] [4] [6] [7].

6 Conclusion

We have shown a raw dependence of gravity on QED. Gravitational acceleration in a context with total spin = 2 seems to be a plausible argumentation. But strange consequences, as described above, could imply this derivation is wrong or partially wrong. However, experimentally finding neutrino without a gravitational field would be a great surprise and a proof in favor of this origin of gravitational field.

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